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Hepatic glucose metabolism in the steatotic liver

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Abstract

The liver is central in regulating glucose homeostasis, being the major contributor to endogenous glucose production and the greatest reserve of glucose as glycogen. It is both a target and regulator of the action of glucoregulatory hormones. Hepatic metabolic functions are altered in and contribute to the highly prevalent steatotic liver disease (SLD), including metabolic dysfunction-associated SLD (MASLD) and metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis (MASH). In this Review, we describe the dysregulation of hepatic glucose metabolism in MASLD and MASH and associated metabolic comorbidities and how advancements in techniques and models for the assessment of hepatic glucose fluxes in vivo have led to identifying the mechanisms related to the alterations in glucose metabolism in MASLD and comorbidities. These fluxes can ultimately increase hepatic glucose production concomitant with fat accumulation and alterations in the secretion and action of glucoregulatory hormones. Nowadays, no pharmacological treatment has been approved for MASLD or MASH, but some antihyperglycemic drugs approved for treating type 2 diabetes have shown positive effects on hepatic glucose metabolism and hepatosteatosis. A deep understanding of how MASLD affects glucose metabolic fluxes and glucoregulatory hormones might assist in the early identification of at-risk individuals and the use or development of targeted therapies.

Key points

- Hepatic glucose metabolism can be studied by measuring metabolite fluxes (fluxomics) based on in vivo infusion of non-radioactive labelled compounds and using metabolic mathematical modelling.
- The liver is the major contributor to endogenous glucose production via gluconeogenesis and glycogenolysis and is the greatest reserve of glucose as glycogen.
- Hepatic glucose metabolism is mainly regulated by glucoregulatory hormones, including insulin and glucagon and by substrate availability.
- Hepatic extraction and clearance of insulin modulates peripheral insulin action and has a role in hyperinsulinemia in steatotic liver disease.
- Abnormal increase in gluconeogenesis and impaired glycogen metabolism are observed in steatotic liver disease and related metabolic conditions such as obesity and type 2 diabetes.
- Hepatic and peripheral insulin resistance and hyperglucagonemia contribute to altered glucose metabolism and the pathogenesis of steatotic liver disease.

Introduction

The liver has a striking metabolic plasticity, shifting adaptively between energy storage and supply depending on nutritional, hormonal, and neural inputs. This feature makes the liver an important hub for the maintenance of metabolic homeostasis. In particular, the liver is crucial for the control of glucose homeostasis by contributing to glucose disposal in the fed state and to glucose production in the fasted state, besides modulating peripheral concentrations of insulin, one of the main glucoregulatory hormones, by clearing the great majority of insulin produced by the pancreas. The control of hepatic glucose metabolism is achieved through both acute regulatory mechanisms involving allosteric modulation, posttranslational modifications (for example, phosphorylation and dephosphorylation), and availability of substrate (for example, glucose, glycerol, alanine, lactate), as well as chronic slow transcriptional mechanisms. The resultant glucose fluxes through gluconeogenesis, glycogenolysis, glycogenesis, and glycolysis, which can be quantified, are critical

determinants of the maintenance of euglycemia and the development of diabetes¹.

Alteration of hepatic regulation of glucose metabolism is a hallmark feature of steatotic liver disease (SLD). SLD encompasses the various aetiologies of steatosis. It includes nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), which has now been termed metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD), defining patients who have hepatic steatosis and at least one of five cardiometabolic risk factors². MASLD, formerly NAFLD, is the most prevalent chronic liver disease, affecting about 38% of the global population, and is strongly associated with features of the metabolic syndrome, including obesity, insulin resistance and type 2 diabetes (T2D)³. MASLD ranges from isolated lipid accumulation or steatosis (metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver, MASL) to its active inflammatory form, metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis (MASH), and can progress to cirrhosis, liver failure, cancer and death⁴.

This Review aims to detail how the liver has a central role in regulating glucose metabolism in SLD and comorbidities like obesity and T2D, the hormonal

regulation of hepatic glucose metabolism, and the therapeutic options to target SLD and the dysregulation of hepatic glucose metabolism. An overview of the techniques currently used to evaluate glucose fluxes in the liver is also presented.

How to investigate hepatic glucose metabolism

This section discusses the techniques currently used to investigate hepatic glucose fluxes in humans (**FIGURE 1**).

FIGURE 1. Overview of the techniques currently used to investigate glucose fluxes in humans.

Labelled compounds infused *in vivo*, for example, ^{13}C -Glucose or deuterated water ($^2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), are used to calculate tracer enrichment in tissues and peripheral circulation non-invasively or for MRS imaging. Labelled fluorodeoxy glucose (^{18}F FDG) is used in combination with PET imaging to study tissue glucose metabolism. Omics measurements could also provide powerful insights into the tissue-specific regulations of metabolic pathways involved in glucose metabolism. Metabolic modelling aims to integrate biological knowledge into mathematical frameworks that enable the estimation of a larger set of metabolic fluxes, otherwise non-detectable.

MRS, magnetic resonance spectroscopy; PET, positron emission tomography

Quantification of hepatic glucose fluxes

Hepatic glucose turnover can be properly investigated by fluxomics, which is based on the infusion of substrate tracers that are molecules labelled with a stable or radioactive isotope⁵, a technique that has been used for more than 40 years^{6,7} in humans. Stable isotope tracers are preferable to radioactive tracers because of their complete safety and because more isotopes can be used, that is, labelled Nitrogen (N) and Oxygen (O) beyond Carbon (C) and Hydrogen (H), which are the usual isotopes used for radioactive tracers⁸.

Hepatic glucose production and turnover have also been investigated by the arterial-venous difference, a technique that requires the measurement of metabolite concentrations in arterial blood and venous drainage samples from a specific tissue, along with the measurement of blood flow through the tissue⁹. The study of the arterial-venous balance of the liver has been successfully performed in animals like dogs or pigs, as shown in the studies by Cherrington and colleagues¹⁰ and by Izzo and colleagues¹¹, but it is an imperfect measure in humans as the portal vein cannot be easily catheterized. In humans, the measurement of hepatic glucose balance is obtained using samples from the hepatic vein and an artery (usually in the arm), and the net balance is obtained by the difference of the arterial and hepatic vein glucose concentrations ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{ml}$) times the blood flow (ml/min per kg body weight)¹². Moreover, this technique only enables for the measurement of the net flow of a metabolite, that is, net uptake or net outflow, whereas the use of tracers not only has the advantage of being less invasive, as it is based on the measurement of tracer enrichment in peripheral blood, but it is the only way to measure the unidirectional substrate flow.

Endogenous glucose production (EGP), which is mainly hepatic glucose production (HGP), comprises the contribution of gluconeogenesis and glycogenolysis. EGP is quantified generally by infusing a glucose tracer labelled with ^{13}C or ^{14}C or with ^2H or ^3H . During static conditions, such as during the fasting state, EGP is measured by the ratio of tracer infusion rate to enrichment or specific activity^{6,7}, whereas during dynamic state (for example, during an oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) or in response to meal tolerance tests (MTT)^{13,14}) glucose turnover is evaluated by mathematical models of tracer enrichment⁵.

The degree of hepatic insulin resistance (Hep-IR) is quantified by measuring the effect of insulin in suppressing EGP. EGP suppression by insulin follows a hyperbolic relationship, as shown by Groop and colleagues, who measured EGP at different doses of insulin infused in humans¹⁵, which justifies the calculation of the Hep-IR index as the product of EGP x insulin⁵. Another important result of the study by Groop and colleagues is that in the presence of Hep-IR, as in obesity and T2D, the curve is shifted to the right, indicating that higher insulin concentrations are needed to suppress EGP^{5,15}.

The separate contribution of gluconeogenesis and glycogenolysis to EGP has been investigated by the infusion of labelled glucogenic substrates as alanine, lactate or glycerol and then mass isotopomer distribution analysis through a calculation based on combinatorial probability¹⁶. The measurement of the incorporation of n stable isotopes in the molecule (M0, M1, M2, ...Mn) determines the newly synthesized fraction of the compounds¹⁶. However, this method assumes that there is a single pool of the precursor, therefore leading to an underestimation of gluconeogenesis. It also has the limitation that only one substrate per time is investigated¹⁸. Landau and colleagues have shown that the most reliable method to measure the percentage of gluconeogenesis contribution to EGP is by ingestion of deuterated water, ²H₂O, as it is rapidly equilibrating with the water pool (that is, tracer steady state) and exchange ²H during glucose production¹⁸. Thus, the enrichment of ²H that is bound at the Carbon in position 5 (C-5) of the newly synthesized glucose is a marker of the glucogenic flux, whereas ²H from body water is bound to C-2 of glucose during both gluconeogenesis and glycogenolysis and is equal to ²H₂O enrichment¹⁸. The percentage of gluconeogenesis is then measured by the ratio of ²H in C-5 to either C-2 or ²H₂O enrichment in blood, measured by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GCMS) after several biochemical reactions^{18,19}. Then glucogenic flux is calculated by multiplying the percentage of gluconeogenesis by EGP flux, measured, for example, by [6,6-²H₂]-glucose infusion, whereas glycogenolysis is measured as the difference between EGP and gluconeogenesis flux²⁰. The procedure is time consuming as the C-5 and C-2 of glucose have to be isolated and then converted to hexamethylenetetramine before GCMS analysis¹⁹. A more practical way to measure deuterium incorporation in C-5 or C-2 is by nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), as it does not require isolation of C-5²¹. However, a limitation of the NMR

technique is the large amount of plasma sample needed, that is, 10-15mL.

The simultaneous administration of multiple tracers is necessary to investigate different pathways. For example, Jones and colleagues used, in humans, stable isotope-labelled tracers combined with isotopomer NMR tracer analysis for fluxomics, specifically [1,6-¹³C₂]glucose for the quantification of EGP, ²H₂O for the contribution of hepatic glycogen, and gluconeogenesis (phosphoenolpyruvate (PEP)) and glycerol to EGP, and [U-¹³C₃]propionate for the quantification of flux through PEP carboxykinase, pyruvate recycling, and the tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle²¹. Perry and colleagues also used a new method (named PINTA; see next paragraph for modelling description) to non-invasively assess rates of hepatic mitochondrial citrate synthase flux (*V_{CS}*) and pyruvate carboxylase flux (*V_{PC}*) in humans that uses combined positional isotopomer NMR and GCMS tracer analysis of plasma following infusion of [3-¹³C]lactate and glucose tracer²².

Earlier studies in humans with ¹³C magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) have been used to quantify the amount of glycogen stored in the liver and, by making multiple measurements over time, the rate of glycogenolysis²³. Gluconeogenesis is then measured as the difference between EGP and glycogenolysis. The advantage is that MRS is noninvasive but requires a probe for ¹³C, high-field instruments and specific expertise.

Positron emission tomography (PET) has also been used in pigs to quantify hepatic glucose fluxes using positron-emitting radionuclide tracers, of which ¹⁸F-fluorodeoxyglucose (FDG) is the most used tracer¹¹. FDG is not metabolized, so PET can detect it once taken up by the liver. The analyses are carried out by quantifying ¹⁸F-FDG in specific regions of interest (ROI), therefore quantifying regional glucose uptake in vivo. For this reason, it is widely applied in the characterization of organ metabolism in humans and animals. The limitations of the PET technique are that it has no spatial definition, so the new instruments are combined with a computed tomography or MRI scan to identify the ROI precisely and quantify the organ dimensions²⁴. Moreover, the tracers are radioactive and have to be synthesized by a cyclotron, but as these isotopes have a limited half-life, the radioactive exposure is also limited²⁵.

Metabolic modelling

The investigation of glucose and tracer turnover in dynamic conditions or the study of intracellular metabolic fluxes often requires mathematical models, such as quantitative frameworks, to describe the functioning and regulation of metabolic networks. Based on the formalization of metabolic reactions, two primary categories of metabolic modelling approaches can be identified, kinetic and constraint-based modelling, and both can rely on label or label-free methodologies. Kinetic models can catch the dynamic nature of biological systems by modelling the metabolic network as a system of kinetic rate law equations and detecting changes occurring in physiological conditions, such as those observed during an OGTT or in response to an MTT. The method called 'PINTA' proposed by Perry and colleagues²² exploits a model of ordinary differential equations previously developed by Katz and colleagues²⁶ under the assumption of a pseudo-steady state and used it to accurately assess the rates of hepatic mitochondrial citrate synthase flux and pyruvate carboxylase flux in vivo. Compartmental modelling is another widely used technique. Compartmental models are lumped parameter models: the events in the system are described by a finite number of changing variables and are, therefore, described by ordinary differential equations¹³. The model equations describe the transfer of both the infused tracer and the endogenous metabolite (tracee), that is, glucose, from one compartment to the next one with the governing law of conservation of mass. The measurements are available in the accessible compartment, whereas the solution of the differential equations enables the estimate of glucose fluxes, including hepatic glucose production, also in non-directly accessible pools¹³. Kinetic modelling has been successfully applied to the study of glucose metabolism and measures metabolic fluxes in humans with high precision, but it is limited to small metabolic networks because of the complexity of determining kinetic parameters. Moreover, the turnover of PET tracers requires mathematical modelling that has been validated versus stable isotope tracers or arterial-venous balance techniques in animal models¹¹.

On the other hand, constraint-based modelling can also be applied to investigate intra-cellular fluxes. It is based on the mass balance between substrates and products of metabolic reactions and their reversibility, often with the assumption of a steady state²⁷. Less accurate than kinetic modelling in determining a specific flux, it has the advantage of inferring metabolic flux through larger metabolic networks. With the current progress in genome sequencing and annotation, the entire cellular

metabolism, that is, the complete set of metabolic reactions occurring inside the cell with their stoichiometry, has been reconstructed for more than 100 organisms, including *Homo sapiens*²⁷. These mathematical models, called genome-scale metabolic models, can be made context-specific by integrating omics data and used to estimate intracellular fluxes by applying constraint-based techniques²⁷. Genome-scale metabolic modelling has been successfully applied to the NAFLD research in humans, mainly exploring hepatic lipid metabolism²⁹⁻³¹ and glucose metabolism and metabolic adaptability in individuals with liver steatosis³². By integrating experimentally measured extracellular fluxes and/or isotope labelling patterns into smaller end-user-curated models, it is possible to obtain more accurate and precise estimates of intracellular fluxome^{33,34}. These methodologies, collectively called isotope-assisted metabolic flux analysis, have been reviewed by Moiz and colleagues³⁵ and are mainly applied to animal models in the study of liver metabolism³⁶, despite their use remains limited.

Hepatic glucose metabolism

The studies that specifically investigated hepatic glucose metabolism and fluxes in individuals with MASLD are limited. However, many clinical studies looked at the separate effects of obesity, T2D, and lipid fluxes on hepatic glucose metabolism, which are of interest given the high prevalence of SLD, over 70%, in these populations³.

Hepatic glucose production and hepatic insulin resistance

It is well established that, in humans, fasting EGP is increased in metabolic diseases like T2D and obesity (**FIGURE 2**). In people with SLD, fasting EGP was found to be either similar³⁷⁻³⁹ or increased⁴⁰⁻⁴³ compared to control individuals, especially if they had T2D. On the other hand, during the postprandial state, impaired insulin-mediated suppression of EGP caused by Hep-IR leads to hyperglycemia and T2D¹.

During fasting and hypoglycemic conditions, the pancreas secretes glucagon, which increases hepatic glucose production (HGP) by stimulating gluconeogenesis (GNG) and glycogenolysis and promotes lipolysis and amino acids catabolism. In the postprandial state, insulin is secreted by the pancreatic β cells and is mainly cleared by the liver during the first pass; the intestine might also contribute to glucagon secretion.

FIGURE 2. The role of insulin resistance in altered glucose metabolism in steatotic liver disease. SLD, steatotic liver disease; TG, triglycerides

Insulin suppresses HGP by inhibiting glycogenolysis and stimulating glycogen synthesis and glucose uptake into insulin-dependent muscle and adipose tissue. It also suppresses lipolysis in adipose tissue and proteolysis in the muscle, therefore reducing substrate fueling into the hepatic GNG flux while stimulating triglyceride synthesis in the liver and adipose tissue. In SLD, insulin resistance is present in muscle, liver and adipose tissue, even in individuals with normal weight and without T2D. The pancreas responds to insulin resistance by secreting more insulin in the portal circulation. The liver also decreases insulin clearance to increase peripheral insulin concentrations. However, HGP and adipose tissue lipolysis are only in part suppressed by insulin due to insulin resistance, resulting in higher fasting plasma glucose and free fatty acid (FFA) concentrations. In muscle tissue, glucose clearance is reduced, whereas proteolysis is not suppressed. Under these conditions, the liver uptake of energy substrates (FFAs, glycerol, alanine, pyruvate, lactate) from peripheral tissues is increased, enhancing hepatic GNG and intrahepatic triglyceride accumulation. Moreover, glucagon resistance and impaired glucagon-stimulated lipolysis and amino acids metabolism develop, leading to fat accumulation and hyperaminoacidemia, which stimulates the pancreatic secretion of glucagon.

Impaired insulin-mediated suppression of EGP, which is an index of Hep-IR, was investigated in people with SLD using tracers combined with the two-step euglycemic hyperinsulinemic clamp (infusing insulin first at 20 mg per kg body weight per min and then at 40 mg per kg body weight per min) investigating the curvilinear relationship between insulin concentrations and EGP (**TABLE 1**). Bugianesi and colleagues showed that in individuals with biopsy-proven SLD but without obesity or metabolic syndrome (n=12), EGP was less suppressed by insulin than in control individuals (n=6), and the curve

insulin-EGP was shifted to the right³⁸. Similar results were shown by Browsers and colleagues, who studied people with (n=17) or without SLD (n=18) and a body mass index (BMI) around 30 kg/m², differentiating the groups for the presence or absence of T2D and finding that, although fasting EGP was not different among groups, individuals with SLD and without T2D (n=11) had reduced hepatic suppression of EGP similarly to individuals with T2D with or without SLD (n=6 and n=7, respectively)⁴⁴. The degree of EGP suppression concerning the degree of intrahepatic triglycerides (IHTG) was also investigated. Ter Horst and colleagues used the two-step insulin clamp in people without T2D, BMI around 40 kg/m² without or with mild to severe steatosis (n=52, 41 and 40, respectively) and showed impaired suppression of EGP during low-dose insulin infusion in individuals with SLD, but similar in mild and severe steatosis⁴⁵. Brill and colleagues reported data from 352 individuals with IHTG measured by MRI also showing that suppression of EGP during low-dose insulin infusion (20 mU per kg body weight per min) was already impaired in people with IHTG=1.5%, that is, below the cut-off of 5.6% that defines SLD, and remained similar in people with a higher degree of steatosis⁴⁶ concluding that a minimum amount of IHTG is sufficient to show impairment in insulin action in the liver. On the other hand, Gastaldelli and colleagues showed that during high-dose insulin infusion (40 mU per kg body weight per min) performed in 57 people with IHTG measured by MRI, EGP was still less suppressed in individuals with SLD and correlated positively with IHTG⁴⁷.

Other conditions of liver disease are also associated with Hep-IR. Vanni and colleagues measured glucose turnover during fasting and hyperinsulinemia euglycemic clamp in 14 individuals with chronic hepatitis C without cirrhosis and 7 controls, finding increased EGP both during fasting and hyperinsulinemic clamp and Hep-IR due to impaired suppression of EGP⁴⁸. In people with cirrhosis from hepatitis C or alcohol, two studies (n=8 patients with cirrhosis and n=4 controls, and n=5 patients with cirrhosis and n=5 controls, respectively) have measured EGP, finding that there was no difference in fasting EGP. However, both studies found an increase in gluconeogenesis, a decrease in glycogenolysis, and an increase in Hep-IR, as shown by increased fasting insulin concentrations^{49,50}.

Fasting Hep-IR, measured as EGP x insulin or by homeostatic model assessment for insulin resistance (HOMA-IR), is also a characteristic feature of individuals with SLD⁵¹ that often shows high fasting insulin, whereas fasting EGP is only increased if they have fasting

hyperglycemia or T2D as first demonstrated in 1989 by DeFronzo and colleagues⁵² and later confirmed by other studies. Rosso and colleagues showed elevated fasting EGP and high insulin levels in 145 people with biopsy-proven SLD without T2D, who also had fasting hyperglycemia⁴³. Previously, Weyers and colleagues had shown that impaired fasting glucose (IFG, that is, glucose 100-126 mg/dl) was associated with increased EGP as well as Hep-IR in 434 Pima Native Americans without T2D⁵³, a population at high risk of T2D and SLD. High fasting glucose, insulin, EGP and Hep-IR were also reported in individuals with MASH by Belfort and colleagues⁵⁴ and Saponaro and colleagues⁵⁵ (n=55 and n=32, respectively).

Elevated EGP in SLD can be multifactorial and related not only to the presence of obesity and/or T2D but also to impaired action of glucoregulatory hormones, including insulin and glucagon⁵⁶. However, the amount of insulin taken up by the liver (that is, hepatic insulin clearance) might have a role, and several studies consistently reported reduced hepatic insulin clearance in people with SLD (see paragraph on hepatic insulin clearance).

Defective suppression of EGP by glucose has been associated with reduced glucose-stimulated flux through glucokinase, a gatekeeper for liver glucose metabolism, and/or an increased flux through glucose-6-phosphatase, a gluconeogenic enzyme⁵⁷ that is upregulated by hyperglycemia⁵⁸, but is also possible that it is owing to clearance of high glucogenic substrates by the liver (see following paragraphs). It is still under debate whether increased EGP and Hep-IR in individuals with SLD are owing to impaired insulin action, hyperglucagonemia and/or decreased glucose clearance. Ter Horst and colleagues have shown that individuals with SLD (n=16) have reduced hepatic activation of insulin receptor kinase (IRK) and AKT in response to glucose or fructose oral challenge taken just before liver biopsy⁵⁹, suggesting a proximal defect in the hepatocellular insulin signalling. Several factors, including certain lipid species, might be responsible for hepatic alterations of insulin signalling. Although intrahepatic lipid accumulation is strongly associated with Hep-IR and consequent perturbation of hepatic glucose metabolism, the mechanisms for lipid-induced Hep-IR (lipotoxicity) are still not completely clear. A major mechanism involves the hepatic accumulation of specific lipid intermediates, such as diacylglycerol (DAG) and sphingolipids, including ceramides and dihydroceramides (markers of de novo ceramide synthesis) rather than triacylglycerol accumulation per se.

Intrahepatic content of DAG—the penultimate intermediate in triglyceride synthesis—is highly correlated with Hep-IR in rats, mice and humans^{45,60-62}. Intracellular DAG, in particular the sn-1,2-DAG stereoisomer, when accumulated in the plasma membrane compartment, but not when associated with lipid droplets or endoplasmic reticulum^{63,64}, has been found to activate and promote membrane translocation of the hepatic protein kinase C (PKC) ϵ , which phosphorylates the IRK at threonine¹¹⁶⁰, therefore impairing IRK activity and insulin signalling leading to Hep-IR⁶⁴. Accordingly, a higher content of plasma membrane-associated sn-1,2-DAG and higher PKC ϵ activation and IRK-threonine¹¹⁶⁰ phosphorylation in liver tissues were related to Hep-IR in humans with SLD^{45,64}. Another mechanism currently proposed for lipid-induced insulin resistance includes sphingolipid species, mostly ceramides (produced by de novo synthesis from fatty acids and sphingosine, by sphingomyelin hydrolysis or by the salvage pathway)⁶⁵. It was shown in mice that ceramides antagonized insulin signalling by activating atypical PKC ζ and protein phosphatase 2A, leading to the inactivation of AKT, an insulin-stimulated kinase crucial for signal transduction⁶⁶. Intrahepatic content of ceramides was increased in the liver of individuals with SLD and associated with whole-body insulin resistance and HOMA-IR, but not with Hep-IR^{45,61,64,66-68}.

Effect of hepatic overflow of free fatty acids on HGP

High free fatty acids (FFA) concentrations due to impaired insulin-mediated suppression of lipolysis in case of insulin resistance are considered among the mechanisms responsible for increased EGP (**FIGURE 2**). In people with obesity, the increased white adipose tissue mass and rate of lipolysis due to adipose tissue insulin resistance increase the plasma concentrations of FFA and glycerol, which are then delivered to the liver, in which they stimulate gluconeogenic flux by providing substrate (glycerol) and activation (FFA)^{17,69,70}. As shown in humans by Donnelly and colleagues⁷¹, 59% of hepatic TAG are derived from FFA, whereas about 26% and 15% of TAG derive from de novo lipogenesis (DNL) and dietary fatty acids, respectively. Lipolysis is increased in individuals with SLD^{55,69}, especially in those with NAFLD activity score 4–6 and fibrosis F2–4 and correlates with hepatic fat and Hep-IR⁵⁵. Similar results were shown by Sunny and colleagues in both mice and humans, showing that increased lipolysis in SLD was correlated with increased mitochondrial TCA activity and anaplerosis^{72,73}. Fletcher and colleagues showed that after 12 hours of

fasting, FFA concentrations were higher in individuals with SLD (n=23) than in controls (n=17), but after 24 hours, only controls further increased FFA concentrations that were higher than in individuals with SLD⁷⁴. Many investigators agree that the adipose tissue-liver cross talk⁷⁵ associates increased lipolysis with hepatic fat accumulation, Hep-IR, and increased gluconeogenesis in humans. Accordingly, the hormonal or pharmacological suppression of lipolysis during fasting reduces the plasma concentrations of FFA and glycerol and the hepatic content of acetyl-CoA and pyruvate carboxylase activity, which was accompanied by suppression of HGP⁷⁶. Earlier tracer studies in healthy humans also supported the relationship between FFA changes and gluconeogenesis during 24 h fasting, showing that the suppression of FFA lipolysis with nicotinic acid was associated with decreased gluconeogenesis, whereas a strong increase in gluconeogenesis was observed during the FFA rebound owing to the disappearance of nicotinic acid⁷⁷. Changes in gluconeogenesis were accompanied by changes in glycogenolysis in the opposite direction⁷⁷. The inhibition of FFA and glycerol turnover is particularly relevant for the acute indirect insulin-mediated suppression of hepatic gluconeogenesis^{78,79}, as described in the following section. On the other hand, lipid infusion (but not glycerol infusion) determined an increase in gluconeogenesis even when controlling for insulin and glucagon concentrations with somatostatin infusion⁸⁰. Visceral adipose tissue (VAT) is more lipolytic than subcutaneous adipose tissue (SAT)⁸¹, and VAT lipolysis is more resistant to insulin-mediated suppression⁸². Moreover, although SAT, with its greater overall mass, contributes more than VAT to circulating FFA, the VAT-derived FFA are released in the portal vein, therefore directly exposing the liver to high FFA concentrations and contributing to the development of steatotic liver and Hep-IR⁸³. In agreement with this portal hypothesis, VAT, but not the fat content in the liver, was associated with the accelerated percentage of gluconeogenesis and gluconeogenesis flux observed in T2D in humans⁴⁷. Using PET and/or computed tomography scans, Iozzo and colleagues showed increased FFA flow to the liver in individuals with obesity, in particular from VAT; moreover, increased FFA was associated with both increased hepatic fatty acids oxidation and re-esterification⁸⁴. Furthermore, FFA overflow to the liver is associated with increased fasting gluconeogenesis, glucose concentrations and Hep-IR, as shown by Gastaldelli and colleagues^{47,85} and Saponaro and colleagues⁵⁵. It is of note that patients with SLD, even with normal weight or overweight, have increased VAT

compared with healthy individuals⁵⁵, impaired lipolysis and elevated plasma FFA^{47,86,87} independently of obesity^{39,55}.

As a further confirmation of the tight relationship between adipose tissue, liver disease, and glucose metabolism, it has been widely shown the positive effect of body weight loss achieved either with diet intervention or bariatric surgery in patients with metabolic diseases leading to reduced risk and remission of T2D^{88,89} and ameliorating liver histology in patients with MASLD⁹⁰⁻⁹². Body weight loss improves insulin sensitivity: a post-hoc analysis showed that weight loss and VAT reduction were associated with improved glucose tolerance⁹³. Moreover, VAT reduction was also associated with reduced liver fat content and the improvement of MASH⁹⁴. These effects can also be achieved with pharmacological intervention, as discussed later.

Hepatic gluconeogenesis and liver disease

Both glycogenolysis and gluconeogenesis contribute to EGP (**FIGURE 3**). Our group was among the first to investigate the contribution of gluconeogenesis to EGP in relation to the presence of obesity and diabetes using ²H₂O. We observed that individuals with obesity and normal glucose tolerance had an increased contribution of gluconeogenesis to total EGP compared to individuals without obesity or T2D (62% versus 47% of EGP). High gluconeogenesis was also found in patients with T2D regardless of the presence of obesity (64% and 68% of EGP in patients with T2D without or with obesity, respectively)²⁰. This finding was confirmed by other studies⁹⁵⁻⁹⁷, indicating that both T2D and obesity are independently associated with increased gluconeogenesis. At that time, the steatotic liver was not considered a disease and not specifically looked for, but most of those patients likely had SLD.

Hepatic gluconeogenesis and glycogenolysis are the main contributors to endogenous glucose production. In gluconeogenesis, irreversible glycolytic reactions are overcome by key gluconeogenic enzymes, including pyruvate carboxylase, phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase (PEPCK), fructose-1,6-bisphosphatase, and glucose-6-phosphatase, which are activated in the fasting state. TCA cycle provides energy and precursors and involves cataplerotic reactions, such as PEPCK, which converts oxalacetate into phosphoenolpyruvate (PEP) to be used for gluconeogenesis, and anaplerotic reactions, including pyruvate carboxylase, which enable gluconeogenic substrates like pyruvate, lactate and

amino acids to enter the cycle and supply gluconeogenesis flux. In the fasting state, adipose tissue lipolysis releases free fatty acids (FFA), which enter the liver and are oxidized to furnish energy for the TCA cycle and gluconeogenesis and yield acetyl-CoA (an allosteric activator of pyruvate carboxylase).

FIGURE 3. Overview of glucose metabolic pathways in the hepatocyte. TCA, tricarboxylic acid cycle; acetyl-CoA, acetyl coenzyme A

Adipose tissue lipolysis also produces glycerol that is phosphorylated in the liver and then converted into the gluconeogenic precursor dihydroxyacetone phosphate (DHAP). Fasting and hypoglycemia and the intestinal hormones glucose-dependent insulinotropic polypeptide (GIP) stimulate the pancreatic secretion of glucagon, which in the liver recruits the cAMP-protein kinase A (PKA) signalling and leads to the transcriptional induction of gluconeogenic enzymes (PEPCK and glucose-6-phosphatase). Glucagon also decreases glycolysis by inhibiting the transcription of hexokinase IV (or glucokinase) and inactivating the glycolytic enzymes liver-type pyruvate kinase and phosphofructokinase-1 whereas activating the gluconeogenic fructose-1,6-bisphosphatase; it stimulates glycogenolysis by activating glycogen phosphorylase and suppresses glycogen synthesis by inhibiting glycogen synthase. Glucagon

stimulates fatty acid oxidation in the liver, fueling the gluconeogenic flux. In the fed state, the pancreas secretes insulin with an incretin effect by GIP and glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1), whereas glucagon release is inhibited. Hepatic insulin signalling (that is, PI3K–Akt) is activated, enhancing glycolysis and the synthesis of glycogen and glycerol and suppressing glycogenolysis. Insulin suppresses hepatic gluconeogenesis by inhibiting the transcription of gluconeogenic enzymes and through the insulin-mediated suppression of adipose tissue lipolysis. Fatty acids, newly synthesized by de novo lipogenesis (DNL) or derived from the diet, are taken up by the liver and used for the synthesis of triglycerides and other lipids (for example, ceramides) or are oxidized to sustain catabolic reactions in mitochondria indirectly.

It is important to emphasize that only in fasting hyperglycemia, that is, in patients with T2D or IFG, was the total EGP flux (the sum of gluconeogenesis and glycogenolysis) increased. Tracer studies found that hyperglycemia was determined by abnormally increased rates of gluconeogenesis rather than glycogenolysis^{20,85,98,99} as in the case of normoglycemia, reduced glycogenolysis compensates for increased gluconeogenesis, a mechanism defined as hepatic autoregulation²⁰. Only a few studies have measured gluconeogenesis in patients with SLD with different results.

Increased gluconeogenesis might depend on circulating glucogenic substrates like glycerol, lactate and alanine or upregulation of glucogenic enzymes. Individuals with increased EGP also showed increased availability of glucogenic substrates that contributed to increased gluconeogenesis and fasting hyperglycemia, as shown in patients with SLD^{74,95,100,101}, T2D^{102,103}, or obesity¹⁰⁴. Moreover, FFA flux increases EGP by impairing hepatic insulin signalling and hence interfering with the direct effects of insulin on the liver glucose metabolism¹⁰⁵⁻¹⁰⁷. Increased transcriptional expression of the gluconeogenic enzymes phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase (PEPCK) and glucose-6-phosphatase, catalytic (G6Pc) has been often associated with increased gluconeogenesis, although Samuel and colleagues showed both in a rat model of diabetic hyperglycemia and in patients with T2D that EGP and gluconeogenesis were increased although no increase was observed in the hepatic expression of PEPCK or G6Pc¹⁰⁸.

As individuals with SLD, obesity or T2D have often increased lipolysis owing to adipose tissue insulin resistance⁷⁵, it was not surprising that the contribution of glycerol to gluconeogenesis was found to be increased in

obesity, T2D or SLD. However, it is still minor compared to the pyruvate carboxylase pathway, that is, from lactate and alanine, both after overnight fasting^{32,69} and after longer fasting, for example, 24h⁷⁴. Glycerol is released by the adipose tissue during lipolysis together with FFA. When taken up by the liver, glycerol is phosphorylated and converted into the gluconeogenic precursor dihydroxyacetone phosphate. On the other hand, FFA, which do not provide net carbon to gluconeogenesis, indirectly fuel the gluconeogenic flux by providing, through their hepatic β -oxidation, the energy needed to drive gluconeogenesis¹⁰⁹ as well as mitochondrial acetyl-CoA that is an allosteric activator of the gluconeogenic pyruvate carboxylase¹¹⁰.

Puhakainen and colleagues found that increased lipolysis and glycerol release were associated with increased EGP and gluconeogenesis from glycerol⁶⁹ in patients with T2D. Hyotylainen and colleagues used genome-scale metabolic modelling to estimate hepatic fluxes in 8 individuals with liver fat between 20–80%, finding that patients with SLD have an upregulation of gluconeogenesis from glycerol rather than from alanine or lactate but similar rates of glycogenolysis³². The increased gluconeogenic flux in obesity was associated with insulin resistance in protein metabolism, leading to increased rates of protein catabolism that provides supplemental amino acids to the liver for glucose production, as shown by Chevalier and colleagues⁹⁵. Interestingly, patients with SLD have increased protein catabolism and sarcopenia¹¹¹, which is further exaggerated in patients with liver cirrhosis that have increased gluconeogenesis but reduced glycogenolysis, therefore maintaining EGP and fasting glycemia within normal ranges⁴⁹.

Hepatic glycogen and liver disease

The liver also represents the greatest reserve of glucose as glycogen, which is synthesised during feeding conditions through glycogenesis and broken down during the fasting state through glycogenolysis to furnish glucose to extrahepatic tissues with a limited reservoir of glucose. The contribution of glycogenolysis (versus gluconeogenesis) to EGP varies according to the metabolic state and decreases with the duration of fasting owing to the depletion of hepatic glycogen storage. Glycogen could also be synthesized through an indirect pathway, that is, from gluconeogenic substrates¹¹².

During fasting, the relative contribution of glycogenolysis and gluconeogenesis to HGP shifts from an initial contribution of glycogenolysis to EGP of 50% at around

12 h fasting to glucose to almost 0% after 40 h fasting when glycogen stores are exhausted, and glucose is almost totally synthesized de novo¹¹³.

Glycogen synthesis and glycogenolysis are regulated by insulin and glucagon in response to changes in glucose concentrations: during fasting state and in hypoglycemia, glucagon stimulates glycogenolysis, whereas when glucose concentrations rise, there is a stimulation in glycogen synthesis (**FIGURE 3**). Petersen and colleagues used ¹³C MRS to measure hepatic glycogen synthesis and glycogenolysis in 29 healthy individuals in different conditions, that is, fasted overnight, euglycemia, or hyperglycemia, and different insulin concentrations, whereas maintaining low glucagon levels through somatostatin infusion¹¹⁴. The investigators found that hyperglycemia and hyperinsulinemia were necessary to promote glycogen synthesis and inhibit glycogenolysis through different mechanisms: hyperglycemia inhibited glycogen phosphorylase flux, whereas hyperinsulinemia stimulated glycogen synthase flux.

A higher hepatic glycogen storage has been reported in patients with T2D and obesity but preserved hepatic autoregulation, that is, increased gluconeogenesis but no increased EGP due to lower glycogenolysis^{96,115}, whereas in individuals with increased EGP, glycogenolysis was increased^{20,42,116}. Hepatic autoregulation is likely mediated by glycogen cycling that is stimulated by insulin. As shown by Petersen and colleagues in conditions of hyperinsulinemia and euglycemia, high hepatic glycogen cycling is associated with reduced net hepatic glycogenolysis and EGP in humans¹¹⁴. Krssak and colleagues⁴² showed an inverse correlation between IHTG and glycogen storage measured by ¹H and ¹³C magnetic resonance spectroscopy during hyperglycemic-hyperinsulinemic-somatostatin clamp in 6 individuals with T2D and 6 controls. Moreover, in people with insulin resistance and MASLD (n=11), Smajis and colleagues¹¹⁷ showed that hepatic glycogen storage was reduced, and hepatic lipid accumulation was stimulated during a mixed meal test compared to healthy individuals (n=10).

Energy metabolism and glucose fluxes

Gluconeogenesis is a highly energetic process and requires large amounts of ATP that are produced either in the TCA cycle or through the oxidation of FFA (**FIGURE 3**). In the TCA cycle, acetyl-CoA, produced by beta-oxidation, is oxidized to CO² to support ATP synthesis via respiratory chain^{118,119} and, in the fasting state, both FFA and several gluconeogenic precursors like pyruvate and amino acids are oxidized to support gluconeogenesis.

The TCA cycle supports both the anaplerotic pathway, in which 4-carbon intermediates enter the cycle, and the cataplerotic pathway, in which intermediates come out of the TCA cycle¹¹⁸. These pathways are particularly important in the liver, providing precursors for ureagenesis, amino acid synthesis, lipogenesis, and primarily gluconeogenesis¹²⁰.

SLD is associated with several mitochondrial alterations^{121,122}. Jin and colleagues found that the rates of gluconeogenesis derived from the TCA intermediates were increased in 19 patients with SLD¹²³. Consistently, Sunny and colleagues showed that flux through anaplerosis and the TCA cycle was increased in 8 individuals with steatotic liver who fasted overnight compared with 8 healthy controls, whereas ketogenesis did not differ⁷³.

The principal anaplerotic reaction is the carboxylation of pyruvate to oxaloacetate and is catalyzed by mitochondrial pyruvate carboxylase, allosterically regulated by acetyl-CoA^{118,119} (**FIGURE 3**). The upregulation of these pathways, essential to gluconeogenesis, is supported by elevated fatty acid oxidation and associated with oxidative stress and inflammation, as shown by Satapati and colleagues^{72,124}. Fletcher and colleagues⁷⁴ confirmed these findings in ketotic conditions and found a blunting in ketogenesis after 24h fasting in patients with SLD (n=23).

Sunny and colleagues showed that increased mitochondrial TCA activity and anaplerosis were also associated with increased lipolysis in mice and humans^{72,73}. Moreover, the increase in TCA flux was followed by the increase in reactive oxygen species production in mice⁷², contributing to the progression to MASH^{124,125}. Koliaki and colleagues found an upregulation of hepatic mitochondrial respiration in individuals with obesity, with and without SLD (n=16 and n=18, respectively), positively correlated with hepatic fat content, plasma FFA and whole-body insulin resistance¹²⁶.

Not all studies are concordant on mitochondrial alterations and progression of SLD towards more advanced forms like MASH with or without fibrosis. Ajaz and colleagues demonstrated a reduction in maximal respiration in patients with SLD and severe fibrosis (n=10) compared to mild or moderate fibrosis (n=10)¹²⁷, and Moore and colleagues found compromised fatty acid oxidation in 56 patients with MASH¹²⁸. To explain the differences in mitochondrial metabolism observed across the spectrum of SLD, Koliaki and colleagues hypothesized an adaptation of hepatic mitochondrial function at the early stages of insulin-resistant SLD, which is subsequently lost in MASH¹²⁶. Nevertheless, other

studies showed elevated beta-oxidation in individuals with MASH¹²⁹, a twofold increase in the oxidative capacity of the TCA cycle and blunted ketogenesis in mice of MASH¹³⁰. Finally, Luukkonen and colleagues found that the increased hepatic mitochondrial redox state is a feature of SLD driven by genetic but not metabolic risk factors and associated with the histological progression of the disease¹³¹.

Genetic factors at the crossroad between hepatic steatosis, insulin resistance and diabetes

Several single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) have been linked to increased risk of MASLD or MASH, such as the protein patatin-like phospholipase domain-containing protein 3 (*PNPLA3*, also called adiponutrin), glucokinase regulator (*GCKR*), transmembrane 6 superfamily member 2 (*TM6SF2*), membrane-bound O-acyltransferase domain-containing 7 transmembrane channel-like 4 (*MBOAT7-TMC4*), whereas others like Kruppel like factor 6 (*KLF6*) and protein 17-beta hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase 13 (*HSD17B13*) were found to protect against steatohepatitis and fibrosis¹³².

Several polymorphisms associated with MASLD or MASH occur in genes that regulate insulin receptor signalling activation (for example, insulin receptor substrate (*IRS1*), mitochondrial function (superoxide dismutase 2 (*SOD2*), uncoupling protein 2 (*UCP2*), amidoxime-reducing component 1 (*MARC1*)). Most of these genes are also associated with increased risk of T2D, such as *IRS1*, *SLC2A1*, *TCF7L2*, and *PPARG*¹³³, whereas for other genes like *PNPLA3*, there was no independent association between the polymorphism associated with MASLD and the increased risk of insulin resistance and/or T2D¹³⁴. However, only a few SNPs concerning glucose metabolism and Hep-IR have been studied.

A meta-analysis that evaluated hepatic and peripheral insulin resistance in individuals with normal glucose tolerance or impaired glucose tolerance genotyped for the *PNPLA3 rs738409* variant showed no association of the SNP with Hep-IR in either group and a mild positive association of the SNP with peripheral insulin sensitivity in individuals with normal glucose tolerance (whereas no effect was observed in those with impaired glucose tolerance)¹³⁵.

The *GCKR rs780094* variant reduces the ability of the *GCKR* to inhibit glucokinase, a key enzyme involved in hepatic glucose uptake and storage¹³⁶. Individuals with this polymorphism are at risk of MASLD but not of T2D¹³⁷. Barata and colleagues¹³⁸ showed that *PNPLA3* and *GCKR* variants interact with insulin resistance

pathways to increase susceptibility to MASLD in patients without T2D. On the other hand, the splice variant *KLF6-SV1* in mouse hepatocytes downregulates GCKR, explaining why *KLF6* polymorphism is associated with delayed histological progression of MASLD and lower Hep-IR measured by tracers¹³⁹.

Meroni and colleagues¹⁴⁰ showed that the MBOAT7 mRNA and protein downregulation in hepatocytes was promoted by hyperinsulinemia and that the downregulation of MBOAT7 in the liver of patients with MASLD was associated with hepatic inflammation, Hep-IR and glucose intolerance independently of MBOAT7 genotype. Zhou and colleagues¹⁴¹ found that individuals carrying the *TM6SF2* variant had increased liver fat content but preserved hepatic and peripheral (adipose tissue) insulin sensitivity.

Hormonal regulation of hepatic glucose metabolism

This section reviews the hormonal mechanisms regulating HGP (**FIGURE 3**). The main gluco regulatory hormones are insulin and glucagon, which are secreted by the pancreatic islets and maintain blood glucose levels within a narrow range¹⁴². Other hormones are also involved in the regulation of HGP, such as incretins, for example, glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1), whose main effect is the potentiation of insulin secretion and the reduction of glucagon secretion, but without an apparent direct action on hepatocytes as no GLP-1 receptors have been found¹⁴³.

Prehepatic insulin secretion, hepatic insulin clearance and insulin action

The pancreatic β -cells secrete insulin into the portal vein, so the liver is the first organ exposed to the newly secreted hormone. Most of the secreted insulin (60–70%) is extracted by the liver, where it is cleared and degraded during the first pass. Only 30–40% of secreted insulin reaches peripheral tissues, after which it is further cleared by the liver during the second pass through the hepatic artery¹⁷. The muscle and the kidney degraded 30–40% of insulin^{47,144,145}. Insulin secretion follows a circadian rhythm with peaks in response to nutrient intake, as the increase in glucose concentration is the main driver of β -cell response.

Insulin regulates glucose tolerance by suppressing EGP in the postprandial state, promoting glycogen synthesis and increasing glucose uptake into insulin-dependent tissues, that is, muscle and adipose tissue. Moreover, insulin acts on adipose tissue lipid metabolism by suppressing peripheral lipolysis and FFA release, stimulating fatty acid

esterification and triglyceride synthesis in the liver and the adipose tissue.

Hepatic insulin action depends on the amount of insulin secreted by the pancreas and taken up by the liver. Indeed, a negative correlation was observed in humans between insulin clearance and Hep-IR¹⁴⁶. Hepatic insulin action is initiated by binding to the insulin receptor and activating the PI3K–AKT (protein kinase B, PKB) pathway. In nondiabetic dogs and humans without T2D, the insulin-mediated suppression of HGP is mediated by direct and indirect (extrahepatic) effects (as reviewed by Lewis and colleagues¹⁴⁷). Insulin signalling acutely and directly stimulates hepatic glucose oxidation (glycolysis) and glycogen synthesis by post-transcriptional (for example, phosphorylation and dephosphorylation) and transcriptional events and also inactivates glycogen phosphorylase, therefore inhibiting glycogenolysis and resulting in net hepatic glycogen synthesis (**FIGURE 3**). Concerning the insulin-dependent suppression of gluconeogenesis, a delayed direct effect is achieved through transcriptional mechanisms conveyed by the AKT-mediated phosphorylation and inhibition of the master gluconeogenic transcription factor forkhead box-containing protein O subfamily-1 (FoxO1).

However, insulin also regulates hepatic gluconeogenesis indirectly via extrahepatic effects through the insulin-mediated suppression of adipose tissue lipolysis and the consequently reduced availability of glycerol and fatty acids for the gluconeogenic flux^{148–150}. Accordingly, studies in mice with genetic defects in hepatic insulin signalling further support the importance of FoxO1 inactivation in the direct insulin action in the liver and the central role for inhibition of lipolysis in the suppression of EGP by insulin also in the absence of hepatic Akt and FoxO1^{151–153}.

Reduced hepatic insulin clearance is a mechanism to increase serum insulin⁴¹ and reduce glucose concentration while preserving glucose tolerance and pancreatic β -cell function in the context of insulin resistance. In an animal model of obesity, insulin resistance and NAFLD (dogs fed with a high-fat isocaloric diet), Kim and colleagues¹⁵⁴ examined the longitudinal changes in insulin secretion and first-pass hepatic insulin extraction, finding that hyperinsulinemia is due mainly to decreased first-pass hepatic insulin extraction whereas portal insulin secretion was increased only in the first weeks of a high-fat diet.

The association between liver steatosis and reduced insulin clearance in adults was observed several years ago (**FIGURE 2**). Insulin clearance measured during insulin infusion (during an euglycemic hyperinsulinemic

clamp) was strongly inversely correlated to increased hepatic fat accumulation, more evident in patients with SLD and T2D^{41,47}. Moreover, reduced insulin clearance was associated with hepatic and peripheral insulin resistance, impaired suppression of EGP, and adipose tissue lipolysis¹⁴⁶. Brill and colleagues demonstrated similar results, with insulin clearance associated inversely with IHTG levels⁴⁶. These associations also hold in children: a multi-ethnic cohort of 632 young individuals, 7-18 years, with obesity and without liver steatosis showed a negative correlation between insulin clearance and hepatic fat content or Hep-IR irrespective of the ethnic background, age, biological sex and adiposity¹⁵⁵. After 2 years of follow-up, an increase in hepatic fat content was associated with a decrease in insulin clearance and an increase in Hep-IR across all groups. Previously, Galderisi and colleagues¹⁵⁶ had shown that the decline in insulin sensitivity in young people with obesity was associated with lowered hepatic insulin clearance even without an impairment of glucose tolerance.

Decreased hepatic insulin clearance might also explain differences in hepatic insulin actions in patients with SLD, as described earlier. However, the mechanisms that explain the differences in hepatic insulin clearance might be related not only to the hepatic expression of insulin receptors but also to the hepatic expression of the carcinoembryonic antigen-related cell adhesion molecule 1 (CEACAM1). It was shown in mice that CEACAM1 promotes hepatic insulin clearance and that upon phosphorylation by the insulin receptor, CEACAM1 promotes receptor-mediated insulin endocytosis and degradation in the hepatocyte, the main mechanism of insulin clearance in the liver¹⁷. Mice lacking Ceacam1 in the liver (*Cc1^{-/-}*) exhibit hepatic steatosis, inflammation, mild basal fibrosis, peripheral hyperinsulinemia, and insulin resistance¹⁵⁷.

Hepatic glucagon action

The pancreatic α -cells secrete glucagon in response to low glucose, high FFA or amino acids (arginine, alanine). Glucagon action in the liver is through the binding to the hepatic G protein-coupled glucagon receptor, resulting in cyclic AMP production and calcium signalling, and involving both transcriptional mechanisms via the expression or activation of the gluconeogenic transcription factor FoxO1 and non-transcriptional mechanisms, ultimately leading to the stimulation of gluconeogenesis and glycogenolysis and the inhibition of

glucose breakdown (glycolysis) and glycogenesis¹⁵⁸ (**FIGURE 3**).

During fasting, glucagon promotes skeletal muscle catabolism and hepatic amino acid uptake to supply amino acids as gluconeogenic precursors and hepatic fatty acid oxidation to supply the energy required to sustain gluconeogenesis while inhibiting DNL. It was shown in dogs that infusion of alanine in the fasting state stimulated α -cell release of glucagon and gluconeogenesis but only in conditions of normal to low glucose and not in hyperglycemia¹⁵⁹. Glucagon, besides increasing gluconeogenesis, promotes hepatic amino acid catabolism via ureagenesis; this liver- α cell axis was shown both in mice¹⁶⁰ and humans^{161,162}. This endocrine regulatory feedback loop seems to be impaired with the development of hepatic steatosis, which could lead to hepatic glucagon resistance to amino acid metabolism, resulting in reduced amino acid clearance and increased plasma concentrations of amino acids^{161,162}. Hyperaminoacidemia induces α -cells hyperplasia and increases glucagon production to compensate for glucagon resistance, resulting in hyperglucagonemia¹⁶¹.

Fasting and postprandial hyperglucagonemia were found in individuals with glucose-tolerant obesity (n=8)¹⁶³ and associated with hepatic steatosis (n=15)¹⁶⁴. Patients with MASLD with (n=10) or without (n=10) T2D showed fasting hyperglucagonemia¹⁶⁵, correlated to elevated plasma levels of amino acids¹⁶⁶. The glucagon resistance to amino acid (and lipid) metabolism (in the face of normal sensitivity to the hyperglycemic effect) could contribute to fasting hyperglycemia and T2D risk in patients with NAFLD¹⁶⁷, having, therefore, clinical and therapeutic implications. Notably, a significant (P<0.001) increase in liver fat was found following chronic treatment of patients with T2D (n=65) with a glucagon antagonist adomeglivant (alternative name LY2409021) compared with sitagliptin (n=41) and placebo (n=68)¹⁶⁸.

The existence of an intrapancreatic cross-talk between insulin and glucagon can have pathophysiological implications in T2D and MASLD. The suppression of glucagon secretion by insulin, in part, might mediate the extrahepatic inhibitory effect of insulin on EGP¹⁶⁹. As reviewed in¹⁷⁰, the loss of this paracrine crosstalk between insulin and glucagon owing to insulin resistance in pancreatic α cells might lead to hyperglucagonemia and increased HGP, as observed in T2D and MASLD. Moreover, glucagon also acts as an insulin secretagogue at high glucose levels, acting through both glucagon receptor and GLP-1 receptors on β cells, and this action has been demonstrated, at least in a mouse model using

isolated perfused pancreas, to be important for appropriate insulin secretion¹⁷¹. Glucagon resistance and hyperglucagonemia might, therefore, contribute to hyperinsulinemia.

New glucoregulatory factors: GLP-1 and bile acids

The incretin hormone GLP-1 is produced in response to an oral intake of nutrients by the entero-endocrine cells within the intestinal mucosa (L cells) through posttranslational modification of proglucagon (the same glucagon precursor)¹⁴³. GLP-1 has both a paracrine mode of action by activating the GLP-1 receptor expressed in the enteric nervous system and vagal afferents and, therefore, triggering the gut-brain-periphery axis, and a direct endocrine mode of action on distant organs, including the pancreas¹⁷². It is an insulinotropic hormone that potentiates glucose-dependent insulin secretion and promotes β -cell growth, whereas it suppresses glucagon secretion through somatostatin induction¹⁴³. In addition to the pancreatic effects, GLP-1 metabolic effects include slowing gastric emptying, inducing satiety with consequent reduced food intake and body weight, and regulating blood flow¹⁴³. Moreover, GLP-1 agonism in humans can improve hepatic insulin sensitivity, with reduction of HGP, DNL and liver steatosis, enhanced hepatic glucose disposal and decreased FFA release by the adipose tissue, independent of weight loss¹⁷³⁻¹⁷⁵. These effects are thought to occur mainly through indirect pancreatic hormones and/or neural-mediated mechanisms because controversy exists regarding the hepatic, muscle and adipose expression of GLP-1 receptors¹⁷⁶⁻¹⁷⁸.

GLP-1 receptor agonists (GLP-1RA) are currently used to treat T2D and obesity; beneficial effects were also observed in patients with MASLD or MASH^{179,180}. **TABLE 2** shows a summary of the main results on MASLD features obtained with the treatment of single GLP-1RA, such as the short-acting exenatide^{174,181-185}, liraglutide^{173,186,187} and lixisenatide¹⁸⁸, and the long-acting GLP-1RA semaglutide¹⁸⁹ and dulaglutide¹⁹⁰, whereas the DPP4 inhibitors, such as sitagliptin, have no effects on hepatic fat¹⁹¹⁻¹⁹³. Only for a few of those compounds have tracer studies been performed in humans to evaluate glucose and lipid fluxes. Currently, no data are available on the effect of the long-acting single, dual or triple GLP-1RA on hepatic glucose fluxes. Indeed, most studies have used exenatide twice daily, administered just before each meal, meaning that the compound concentration raises similarly to the endogenous hormone. Our group has

demonstrated that the effect of exenatide on postprandial glucose fluxes in humans is acute and can be observed with just one dose^{174,194}. Exenatide reduced postprandial glucose concentrations by decreasing glucose absorption and hepatic glucose production while stimulating hepatic glycogen synthesis¹⁷⁴. A decrease in glucagon concentrations might also have a role, but the effects on HGP were also seen in the absence of effects on glucagon concentrations¹⁷⁴. A similar mechanism also explained the anti-hyperglycemic effect of the DPP4 inhibitor sitagliptin in 50 patients with T2D¹⁹⁵. However, sitagliptin had no effect on MASLD (**TABLE 2**). Considering the lack of GLP-1 receptors in the liver, the effect on hepatic glucose production is likely indirect, as HGP can be modulated by the central nervous system (CNS), as recently reviewed by Lewis and colleagues¹⁴⁷. This central effect is consistent with previous studies that have shown that GLP-1–GLP-1RA administration activates the CNS, particularly the hypothalamic area, both during fasting and an oral glucose tolerance test, that is, during the time of action of this hormone¹⁹⁶. A similar effect was also observed by Seghieri and colleagues¹⁷⁵, who infused GLP-1 during a 2 h pancreatic clamp in humans, that is, under conditions mimicking a diabetic fasting state but controlling insulin, glucagon and glucose changes. Under these conditions, GLP-1 infusion suppressed EGP without affecting lipolysis or oxidation of carbohydrates and lipids. The effect of long-acting GLP-1RA on hepatic glucose metabolism is probably through the chronic activation of the CNS, although this central effect might potentiate the effect of endogenous gastric incretin hormones that are still released in response to food intake. Considering that chronic treatment with GLP-1RA leads to substantial weight loss, it is also possible that other chronic effects, like the decrease in fasting hyperglycemia, might also be owing to weight changes.

A new class of drugs, that is, the dual or triple incretins that include GLP-1–glucose-dependent insulinotropic polypeptide (GIP), GLP-1–glucagon (GCG) and GLP-1–GIP–GCG receptor agonists are effective on weight loss, hepatic steatosis, and glucose metabolism (**TABLE 2**). Tirzepatide, a GLP-1–GIP receptor agonist currently approved for the treatment of T2D and under investigation for the treatment of MASH, reduced hepatic fat, body weight and visceral fat in 222 patients with T2D¹⁹⁷ and has shown superior effects compared to semaglutide 1mg dose in weight loss and insulin sensitivity in 45 patients with T2D¹⁹⁸. GLP-1–GCG receptor agonists are under investigation for the

treatment of MASH¹⁹⁹⁻²⁰¹. Phase II studies with cotadutide (n=25)²⁰¹ and efinopegdutide (n=72)¹⁹⁹ have shown a reduction in hepatic fat and markers of liver disease, and cotadutide and BI456906–survodutide, but not efinopegdutide, showed improvement in glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) levels. The triple agonist retatrutide is expected to be superior to single and dual GLP-1RA in decreasing hepatic fat, body weight and glucose metabolism in humans^{202,203}. However, data on hepatic glucose fluxes are still lacking. It would be of particular interest to evaluate glucose fluxes in the GLP-1R–GCG receptor agonists, as glucagon has a stimulatory effect on glucose production. However, considering the lowering effect on HbA1c of most of these compounds, it is likely that the glucagon effect might be counteracted by the GLP-1R effect, likely through the increased insulin secretion. Moreover, weight loss might also reduce gluconeogenic substrate flux to the liver, preventing the rise in gluconeogenesis.

A role in regulating glucose metabolism has emerged for bile acids, a large class of steroid molecules synthesized from cholesterol in the liver. Besides their role in nutrient digestion and adsorption, bile acids regulate hepatic glucose metabolism and thus represent pharmacological targets for therapeutic intervention in MASLD and MASH²⁰⁴. Accordingly, altered bile acid metabolism in the liver²⁰⁵ and changes in circulating bile acid profile²⁰⁶ have been documented in patients with MASLD or MASH. Bile acid signalling is mediated by activating the plasma membrane Takeda G-protein coupled receptor 5 (TGR5) and the nuclear receptor farnesoid X receptor (FXR). As reviewed²⁰⁷, the activation of hepatic FXR signalling or the FXR-mediated induction of intestinal fibroblast growth factor 19 (FGF-19) was shown in mice to improve post-prandial glucose metabolism in the liver by repressing the expression or activation of gluconeogenic pathway and inducing glycogen synthesis. Moreover, hepatic DNL is inhibited²⁰⁸, and fatty acid β oxidation is stimulated²⁰⁹. Activation of TGR5 in the intestine might indirectly improve glucose metabolism by inducing the secretion of GLP-1 by the intestine and insulin by the pancreas²¹⁰. Although overall effects open new potential therapeutic avenues targeting bile acids-associated signalling pathways in MASLD and MASH²⁰⁷, inconsistencies have been found in mouse model studies regarding the effect of agonism or antagonism of intestinal FXR on glycemic control, and unrestricted FXR activation in clinical trials is also accompanied by undesired effects such as a pro-atherogenic lipid profile, pruritus and hepatic toxicity; therefore, many open

questions on this therapeutic strategy in metabolic disease still remain.

Conclusions

Dysregulation in hepatic glucose metabolism is as important as hepatic lipid metabolism in MASLD, and hepatic glucose and lipid metabolism are closely interrelated. Thus, the mechanisms associated with the alterations in glucose metabolism in MASLD should be evaluated as they are strictly related to T2D, driven by obesity and excess lipid flux to the liver.

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Author contributions

The authors contributed equally to all aspects of the article.

Competing interests

A.G. has served as a consultant for: Boehringer Ingelheim, Eli Lilly and Company, Metadeq Diagnostics and Fractyl Health; has participated in advisory boards for: Boehringer Ingelheim, Merck Sharp & Dohme, Novo Nordisk, Metadeq Diagnostics and Pfizer; and has received speaker's honorarium and other fees from: Eli Lilly and Company, Merck Sharp & Dohme, Novo Nordisk, and Pfizer

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TABLE 1. Tracers human studies investigating EGP and insulin resistance in SLD.

Methodology	Disease stage	Results and conclusions	Refs
Infusion of [6,6-2H2]glucose during fasting together with 2H2O during fasting and during high glucagon +octreotide infusion	Cirrhosis from combined hepatitis C and alcohol (n=5)	Similar fasting EGP but increased gluconeogenesis, reduced glycogenolysis and increased insulin in cirrhotic, indicating hepatic insulin resistance	50
Infusion of [6,6-2H2]glucose during fasting together with 2H2O	Cirrhosis from hepatitis C (n=8)	Similar fasting EGP but increased gluconeogenesis, reduced glycogenolysis and increased insulin in patients with cirrhosis, indicating hepatic insulin resistance	49
Infusion of [3-3H]glucose during fasting and low-dose hyper-insulinemic euglycemic clamp	Individuals with different degrees of liver steatosis without obesity or T2D (n=30)	Similar EGP during fasting but higher during the clamp in SLD that also had increased hepatic insulin resistance	39
Infusion of [6,6-2H2]glucose during fasting and hyperglycemic-hyper-insulinemic-somatostatin clamp. Hepatic glycogen concentrations were measured using 13C nuclear MRS after [1-13C]glucose ingestion during meal test	Individuals with SLD and T2D but without obesity (n=6)	Increased EGP and lower hepatic glycogen during the fasting state. Increased EGP and reduced glycogen synthesis in T2D during a meal and insulin infusion. Glycogen synthesis was negatively associated with IHTG	42
Infusion of [6,6-2H2]glucose during fasting and two-step hyper-insulinemic euglycemic clamp	SLD in individuals without obesity or T2D (n=12)	Similar EGP during fasting and clamp but increased hepatic insulin resistance in individuals with SLD	38
Infusion of [6,6-2H2]glucose during fasting and hyper-insulinemic euglycemic clamp. Gluconeogenesis and hepatic glycogen concentrations were measured using 13C nuclear MRS	Individuals with SLD, obesity and T2D (n=8) before and after weight loss were compared with people without obesity (n=10)	Increased EGP, gluconeogenesis and hepatic insulin resistance than controls that were reduced and no longer significant after weight loss and normalization of IHTG	40
Infusion of [6,6-2H2]glucose during fasting and hyper-insulinemic euglycemic clamp together with 2H2O	SLD in people with obesity or T2D (n=43)	Increased hepatic insulin resistance in people with SLD was more evident if they also had diabetes. Increased EGP during clamp in SLD and T2D. Gluconeogenesis was not associated with IHTG but with VF	47
Infusion of [3-3H]glucose during fasting and low-dose hyper-insulinemic euglycemic clamp	SLD with (n=34) or without T2D (n=34)	Increased hepatic insulin resistance in people with SLD was more evident if they also had T2D. Increased EGP in T2D	41
Infusion of [6,6-2H2]glucose during fasting and hyper-insulinemic euglycemic clamp	People with chronic hepatitis C without metabolic syndrome (n=14)	Increased EGP and hepatic insulin resistance	48
Infusion of [3-3H]glucose during fasting and OGTT	People with MASH and IGT or T2D (n=52)	Increased hepatic insulin resistance	54
Infusion of [3,4-13C2]glucose during fasting and hyper-insulinemic euglycemic clamp with 2H2O	African American or Latino and/or Latina individuals with overweight or obesity and elevated liver enzymes (n=16)	Increased EGP in SLD due to gluconeogenesis and anaplerosis and high hepatic insulin resistance	73
Infusion of [3,4-13C2]glucose during fasting and hyper-insulinemic euglycemic clamp with 2H2O	Men with SLD without T2D (n=19)	Increased EGP during the clamp and higher hepatic insulin resistance. Increased gluconeogenesis from PEP in SLD	123
Infusion of [6,6-2H2]glucose	People with MASH without T2D (n=145)	Increased EGP and hepatic insulin resistance in individuals with SLD	43
Infusion of [6,6-2H2]glucose during fasting and two-step hyper-insulinemic euglycemic clamp	People with severe obesity and different degrees of liver steatosis (n=133)	Similar EGP during fasting but increased during the clamp in SLD that also had higher hepatic insulin resistance associated with hepatic cytosolic DAGs more than to IHTG	45
Infusion of [3-3H]glucose during	People with different	Impaired suppression of EGP during clamp is	46

fasting and low-dose hyper-insulinemic euglycemic clamp	degrees of liver steatosis and/or obesity or T2D (n=144)	already evident in people with IHTG>1.5% and constant on SLD regardless of the amount of IHTG content	
Infusion of [6,6-2H2]glucose during fasting and two-step hyper-insulinemic euglycemic clamp	Individuals with SLD, overweight or obesity (n=11) or T2D (n=13)	Impaired suppression of EGP is similar in people with SLD or T2D, but increased hepatic insulin resistance in SLD	44
Infusion of [6,6-2H2]glucose during fasting and two-step hyper-insulinemic euglycemic clamp	People with SLD and overweight or obesity (n=13)	Similar suppression of EGP and hepatic insulin resistance. Reduced hepatic insulin clearance in SLD but not associated with suppression of EGP	37
Infusion of [3,4-13C2]glucose during fasting and hyper-insulinemic euglycemic clamp with 2H2O	People with SLD without T2D and BMI >35 kg/m2 (n=40)	The majority of glucose from gluconeogenesis originated from pyruvate carboxylase, minor contribution of glycerol	74
Infusion of [6,6-2H2]glucose during fasting and two-step hyper-insulinemic euglycemic clamp. Liver biopsy after drinking 75g of glucose or fructose (2h before biopsy) and 2H2O (the night before) to measure DNL	People with severe obesity without T2D (n=16)	Similar EGP during fasting but increased during the clamp in SLD that also had increased hepatic insulin resistance and reduced insulin signalling in response to glucose and fructose load and glycogen synthesis	59
Infusion of [6,6-2H2]glucose	People with MASH without T2D (n=32)	Increased EGP and hepatic insulin resistance in people with SLD associated with both IHTG and VF	55

BMI, body mass index; EGP, endogenous glucose production; DAG, diacylglycerol; DNL, de novo lipogenesis; IGT, impaired glucose tolerance; MASH, metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis; MRS, magnetic resonance spectroscopy; OGTT, oral glucose tolerance test; PEP, phosphoenolpyruvate; SLD, steatotic liver disease; IHTG, intrahepatic triglycerides; T2D, type 2 diabetes; VF, visceral fat.

TABLE 2. Incretin-based drugs for the treatment of SLD and their effect on glucose metabolism.

Drug name; mode of administration	Regulatory status	Steatosis	Fibrosis markers	Hepatic enzymes	HbA1c	Insulin resistance	References
GLP-1 receptor agonist							
Liraglutide; SC	Phase IV (n=14, n=26, n=22)	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓Related to weight loss	173,186,187
Semaglutide; SC or PO	Phase IV (n=957)	NA	NA	↓	↓	↓Related to weight loss	189
Dulaglutide; SC	Phase IV (n= 1499)	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓Related to weight loss	190
Exenatide; SC	Phase IV (n=15, n=33, n=60, n=217, n=695, n=76)	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓Related to weight loss	174,181-185
Lixisenatide; SC	Phase IV	NA	NA	↓	↓	↓Related to weight loss	188
DPP4 inhibitor							
Sitagliptin; PO	Phase IV (n=50, n=7, n=12)	=	=	=	↓	=	191-193
GLP-1-GIP							
Tirzepatide (LY3298176); SC	Phase IV (n=296, n=117)	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	197,198
GLP-1-glucagon							
Cotadutide (MEDI0382); SC	Phase II (n=61)	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	201
Survodutide (BI456906/ZP2929); SC	Phase III (n=24)	↓ ^a	↓ ^a	NA	↓ ^a	↓	200
Efinopegdutide (HM12525A-MK-6024); SC	Phase II (n=145)	↓	↓	↓	=	NA	199
GLP-1-GIP-glucagon							
Retatrutide; SC	Phase II (n=275, n=338)	↓ ^a	↓ ^a	↓ ^a	↓	↓ ^a	202,203

GLP-1: glucagon-like peptide-1; GIP: glucose-dependent insulinotropic polypeptide; IR: insulin resistance; SC: subcutaneous; PO: per os (oral administration); SLD, steatotic liver disease

^a preclinical data.